

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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IDENTIFICATION OF CARADIOGENIC SHOCK IN EMERGENCY TRIAGE NURSING

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The lack of a standardized process for early identification and differentiation of cardiogenic shock (CGS) leads to a delay in the initiation of targeted treatment, increasing patient mortality risk. The seven-step Iowa model was used as the framework for this quality improvement project. The project resulted in an algorithm to assist in the early identification of CGS during triage in the Emergency Department (ED). It included clinical criteria for shock, nurse-initiated orders, and process steps for identifying and classifying patients in the triage process. CGS is difficult to differentiate from other forms of shock; however, differentiation is vital to treatment as CGS requires a different treatment. CGS is a complex, life-threatening condition with high mortality rates exceeding 50%. Evidence supports using algorithms and protocols to facilitate early identification and treatment to improve patient outcomes. The developed algorithm provided direction for the triage nurse in the initial evaluation and recognition of CGS. An easy-to-follow algorithm assists the triage nurse in the initial assessment and rapid recognition of CGS, allowing for vital and timely targeted treatment initiation.

Keywords: CGS triage, triage, CGS differentiation

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Background

Shock is a life-threatening emergency that, when left untreated, will result in inadequate end-organ perfusion, leading to multisystem failure and death (Keller, 2019). Shock leads to the body's inability to supply oxygen and nutrient-rich blood to tissues and vital organs. Proper assessment and evaluation are crucial to the management of shock. There are multiple etiologies of shock, such as cardiogenic shock (CGS) caused by myocardium failure, septic shock caused by severe infection, hypovolemic shock due to blood loss or dehydration, and neurogenic shock, which is secondary to neurologic dysfunction. CGS is a life-threatening emergency, with a mortality rate exceeding 50% (Tehrani et al., 2018). In 2018, the incidence of CGS rose to 103 per 100,000 hospitalizations (Osman et al., 2021). The most common causes of CGS were due to acute myocardial infarction (AMI) or acute decompensated heart failure (ADHF). In 2013, the cost of caring for patients with an AMI or heart failure (HF) was \$21.1 billion and \$30.8 billion, respectively. In 2023, HF care costs were estimated to increase by 127%, equating to \$69.7 billion (Benjamin et al., 2018).

Little progress has been made over the past 20 years in improving CGS mortality rates despite new therapies, such as mechanical support and early percutaneous coronary interventions (Basir et al., 2019). Despite the advances, there continue to be delays in recognition and appropriate treatment, which have been attributed to the fragmentation of care and practice pattern disparities (Moghaddam et al., 2021). Until recently, there has not been a focus on standardizing care for patients in CGS, which should begin at the initial triage stage when a patient presents with symptoms to the ED. There are opportunities to intervene with these patients to help mitigate CGS's adverse long-term effects.

In contrast to CGS, septic shock has gained attention in recognition and treatment due to the Surviving Sepsis Campaign (SSC), which updated the international guidelines in 2021 (Evans et al., 2021). These SSC guidelines provided recommendations based on best practices to guide clinicians in caring for patients with sepsis or septic shock and have proven to reduce mortality when adhered to (Evans et al., 2021). Septic shock requires prompt treatment, with an hour delay in treatment reflecting a 7.6% decrease in survival. The lack of appropriate and timely treatment contributed to these high mortality rates (Nevill et al., 2021). The SSC guidelines have demonstrated improved patient outcomes as increased acuity correlated with decreased time in ED and transfer to nursing areas to provide appropriate treatment (Nevill et al., 2021). Like the SSC, education and screening tools can be implemented to promote early identification and differentiation of CGS to provide appropriate treatment, leading to improved outcomes.

Shock Etiology

In general, a variety of shock phenotypes can cause a patient to experience decreased blood flow, resulting in a lack of perfusion to all vital organs: the brain, heart, liver, lungs, kidneys, and intestines (Henry et al., 2021). These different phenotypes are defined by the physiological changes happening in the body that require individualized treatments since one treatment may cause harm to another form of shock. Common treatments associated with shock may include fluid resuscitation, mechanical ventilation to take over the work of the lungs, and intravenous medications known as vasoactive and inotropes that help increase blood pressure or enhance the myocardium pumping to circulate blood through the body.

Hypovolemic shock is due to insufficient blood volume, commonly caused by blood loss or dehydration, which requires replenishment of fluids or blood. Septic shock is caused by an illness, releasing toxins into the bloodstream. The primary treatment for septic shock is

identifying and resolving the infection while supporting blood flow and bodily functions until the condition resolves (Sakr et al., 2020). CGS, however, is a complex, multifactorial syndrome characterized by myocardium “pump” failure resulting in low cardiac output and end-organ hypoperfusion (Lee et al., 2020).

The most common causes of CGS are AMI, ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), or ADHF. During an AMI or heart attack, blood flow to the heart muscle is decreased due to a blockage in one of the coronary arteries. Rapid intervention is required to open the artery, allowing restoration of blood flow to the myocardium with minimal long-term damage, and has shown survival benefits (Henry et al., 2021). The longer the myocardium is without this vital blood flow, the more potential damage is done. The myocardium often does not return to normal after prolonged periods without blood flow, resulting in cardiomyopathy, commonly called HF, which results in the myocardium’s inability to pump adequate blood for normal activities of daily living. The decrease in forward flow prevents sufficient blood from reaching vital organs, slowly damaging the organs. HF is a chronic disease that may present with intermittent exacerbations of varying severity, known as ADHF, which may require hospitalization with aggressive treatment and can result in cardiogenic shock.

Cardiogenic shock resulting from an AMI or ADHF causes hypoperfusion of vital organs such as the liver, lungs, kidneys, intestines, and heart (Pirrota et al., 2021). Treatment with aggressive diuretics to remove excess fluid, mechanical ventilation, and vasoactive and inotrope medications may not be enough. The heart may need more support from motorized devices temporarily placed inside the body, called mechanical circulatory support. Several types are available, providing differing levels of support, and they are selected based on the individual’s heart and body needs.

Due to the complexity of the illness, patients in CGS often have longer lengths of stay, with increased medication use, mechanical ventilation, and MCS usage (Jentzer et al., 2019). Patients who survive until hospital discharge may be transferred to facilities for rehabilitation or long-term care homes due to the inability to return to a previous level of function. During an acute illness or decompensation, families can spend extended periods at the hospital, experiencing grief and emotional distress beyond the hospitalization (Norkiene et al., 2019). Sometimes, despite maximum efforts, treatment fails to improve the patient's condition, and family and loved ones are called upon to make the difficult decision to withdraw or withhold life-sustaining efforts. The healthcare costs associated with heart disease are estimated to be \$216 billion annually (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2023). Myocardial infarction care is one of the ten most expensive conditions to treat, costing \$12.1 billion (Benjamin et al., 2018). The prevalence among American adults with HF between 2011 and 2014 was estimated at 6.5 million, with an estimated total cost of care in 2012 of \$30.8 billion (Benjamin et al., 2018). This is projected to increase by 127% to \$69.7 billion by 2030 (Benjamin et al., 2018).

The emergency nature of CGS, the associated high mortality rates, and the economic costs of medical care call for intensive efforts to improve prompt recognition, appropriately diagnose, and treat this population of patients to improve outcomes. The need for early intervention based on accurate assessment and differentiation of shock etiology has led hospitals and providers to evaluate and improve how they initially triage patients in the ED. The number of institutions evaluating and adopting a multidisciplinary team-based strategy, including protocols to guide care, is increasing (Basir et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2020; Tehrani et al., 2019).

Problem Statement

The problem this project addressed was the lack of standardization in the early recognition and accurate identification of patients in CGS during the initial triage process in the ED. Specialized treatment plans are required based on shock etiology, which can be first identified during initial triage. A standardized initial triage process can facilitate early shock recognition and accurate differentiation of CGS from other shock etiologies. Rapid initial recognition of CGS results in results in immediate initiation of targeted treatment, therefore decreasing the risk of morbidity, mortality, emotional distress, and rising costs of caring for patients with CGS.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to address the need for consistent, timely, and accurate diagnoses and differentiation of shock etiology to ensure the best patient outcomes. The aim of the project is to design an algorithm to assist frontline nursing staff in recognizing shock quickly, triage patients according to their initial presenting symptoms, and begin the pathway to differentiation of CGS. The ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI), stroke, and sepsis models were utilized to develop the algorithm for the identification of CGS. Current literature on early recognition of CGS was used to create an algorithm for early recognition and differentiation at the initial patient presentation was developed. The algorithm includes definitions of CGS, criteria based on symptoms, and appropriate steps. This algorithm includes vital signs, recommended testing, and hemodynamic parameters that are recognized by several medical societies and associations that set the standards of care for CGS, such as the American College of Cardiology, the American Heart Association, the Society of Critical Care Medicine, and the Society of Thoracic Surgeons (Baran et al., 2019).

Project Objectives

This project consisted of several objectives, which outline the anticipated outcomes of early identification of CGS:

- Nursing education on signs and symptoms of CGS.
- Increase nurse confidence in recognizing CGS due to education.
- Ability to classify patient acuity based on Society of Cardiovascular Angiography and Intervention (SCAI) shock stages.
- Nurse-initiated orders for early identification of CGS.
- Development of an algorithm based on evidence-based practice (EBP) to standardize care for patients presenting with symptoms of CGS.

Supporting Framework

A theoretical framework helped to guide the project and provided a lens through which the project was interpreted. The Iowa model of research-based practice to promote quality care (Appendix A) guided this project (Buckwalter et al., 2017). This model was developed by nurses at the University of Iowa in the early 1990s and continues to be used by nurses and other healthcare providers in evaluating and integrating research into patient care. It provides a conceptual framework focused on organization and collaboration to guide the implementation of EBP (White & Spruce, 2015). This model is an application-oriented framework of seven steps to guide the change process to assist nurses in effectively implementing EBPs, using a pilot test before full-scale implementation (Cullen et al., 2022).

The Iowa model has been used to facilitate the translation and implementation of evidence into practice. In 2021, it was successfully used to implement a decision-support algorithm for pain assessment in a combined cardiac and medical Intensive Care Unit (ICU). The

framework guided the improvement in practice and helped facilitate the integration and sustainability of the improved process. Key stakeholders and change champions participated in designing and implementing the algorithm with practice prompts to improve compliance (Laures et al., 2021).

Integration of the Iowa Model

The first step in the Iowa model was to identify and select a trigger or problem. This project addressed the need for knowledge of shock pathophysiology and the development of an algorithm to standardize early recognition of CGS while differentiating it from other shock etiologies. This step also included determining if an algorithm was appropriate to promote the needed change in practice (Brown, 2014). The purpose of the project was to design and implement an algorithm to improve the process and outcomes for CGS patients. It provided nursing staff with a standardized workflow for initial assessment and triage. The outcomes included an increase in the early recognition and differentiation of CGS. Several studies have identified that using algorithms has effectively decreased CGS mortality through prompt targeted treatment (Lee et al., 2020; Papolos et al., 2021; Tehrani et al., 2019).

The second step determined that the topic was a priority for the organization. The high mortality rate associated with CGS and the lack of consistency in diagnosing shock etiology resulted in the delay of definitive treatment. There is an opportunity to improve patient care by developing an algorithm to guide triage nurses in recognizing and differentiating CGS. There are secondary benefits to providing prompt, targeted treatment for patients with CGS, which include cost reduction, shorter ICU and hospital stays, and decreased need for advanced therapy (Duncan et al., 2019).

The third step in the model was forming a team that included key stakeholders who would participate in developing an algorithm to direct nurses at the triage stage in recognition of CGS. This interdisciplinary team included physicians, nursing educators, and nursing directors. The multidisciplinary team provided various viewpoints on the process. It investigated how the algorithm would affect the departments and staff and identified potential obstacles and resources available to each. The information obtained was considered when developing the algorithm and developing or planning the necessary training.

The fourth step involved gathering and assembling relevant research and related literature to collect the available knowledge on CGS care involving protocols and triage algorithms. Research studies and clinical practice guidelines were considered. Clinical practice guidelines are based on evidence and systematic reviews of evidence reviewed by peers and multidisciplinary panels, who then make recommendations (White & Spruce, 2015). The search details and findings are found in the literature review section, which follows in this paper. Each study was critically appraised for quality and consistency regarding CGS. The research and guidelines were appraised and synthesized. Sufficient evidence was available to support the design of an algorithm to guide the care of patients with CGS.

With sufficient evidence, step five included designing and piloting the change. The algorithm was created to standardize the triage nurse process in promptly recognizing shock and differentiating CGS from other types of shock. The protocol is based on research evidence and evidence-based guidelines from the literature search, review, and evaluation. Three subject matter experts reviewed the algorithm to ensure accuracy and ease of use. The subject matter experts were board-certified physicians who were experts in treating patients with CGS. The subject matter experts read the algorithm and provided expert opinions regarding the accuracy of

the content and whether nurses could implement the algorithm. The experts recommended changes to the criteria identification of shock, which were incorporated into the final algorithm. If evidence had not been available, opinion papers written by experts in the field, small pilot studies, and institutional or national outcomes could be used to base practice. Another option not pursued in this project would be conducting further research.

The next final steps in the Iowa model consisted of integrating and sustaining the practice change. Due to time constraints, pilot implementation and necessary education of participants will occur after this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) program is completed. After completion of the DNP program, the algorithm will be implemented in the ED. The final decision in the Iowa process is to determine if the pilot results demonstrated that the algorithm would be incorporated as a new practice as designed. After completion of this DNP program, the implementation process will be monitored, and the structure, process, and outcome data will be analyzed. The results will be disseminated at committee meetings, staff meetings, and via email announcements.

Review of Literature

Overview

A literature search was conducted using the Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINHAL), PubMed, Google Scholar, and OneSearch for current CGS identification and care studies. Search terms included “cardiogenic shock,” “CGS,” “shock,” “shock protocols,” “cardiogenic shock treatment,” “team-based care,” “protocol-based care,” “diagnosis of cardiogenic shock,” “shock team,” “shock triage,” “emergency triage,” “nurse triage,” “triage,” “septic shock triage,” “POCUS,” “pulmonary artery catheter,” and “non-invasive hemodynamic monitoring,” “Iowa model,” “evidence-based practice.” Few randomized trials or prospective studies for ED evaluation and management of CGS are currently available.

The inclusion criteria included articles on shock treatment protocols, triage processes, laboratory, and hemodynamic monitoring. The initial search resulted in 997 articles. Articles that included the pediatric population, focused on mechanical circulatory support, and those not written in English or published before 2018 were excluded, reducing the number of articles to 169. The reference sections of select articles were reviewed based on their relevance to the project’s purpose. This yielded an additional seven articles, which totaled 176. The titles and abstracts of the remaining 176 articles were reviewed for protocols related to CGS care; additionally, duplicates were excluded. In total, 15 articles from 176 are included in the project.

Iowa Model

Research often leads to EBP guidelines. A study indicated that nurses value EBP, although they lack the education and time to translate these into practice. These guidelines can improve patient care and outcomes while controlling healthcare costs (Brown, 2014). Translating the research and guidelines into practice can be challenging and may take years. Nurses have

used the Iowa model to structure and guide this process (Brown, 2014; Laures et al., 2021).

Laures et al. (2021) utilized the Iowa model to implement an algorithm in the ICU to improve practice, which was integrated into the facility and has been sustained. The Iowa model provides step-by-step guidance through questions and crucial decision points (Titler et al., 2001).

Protocol Driven Care

One of the strategies used to facilitate timely care in the ED has been nurse-initiated medications (Cabilan & Boyde, 2017). Triage nurse ordering before a provider sees the patient has been proven to reduce the time for providing interventions for patients with various conditions such as fractures, pain, wheezing (asthma), and chest pain. Several studies have demonstrated that timely nurse initiation orders for treating patients in triage have provided more immediate care than waiting until after the provider evaluation (Cabilan & Boyde, 2017; Hwang et al., 2016; Rowe et al., 2011). The order set for triage nurses to initiate care for patients with chest pain significantly decreased the time from presentation to treatment by 16.9% ($p=0.04$) (Hwang et al., 2016).

The use of an algorithm has been validated and effective in reducing time to definitive care and mortality in patients with STEMI (Kontos et al., 2020; O’Gara et al., 2013). Several studies report decreased mortality associated with a team-based approach based on algorithms for patients in CGS (Basir et al., 2019; Tehrani et al., 2019; Truesdell et al., 2018). Based on the emergent nature of CGS, an algorithm like those used in these other emergencies would also be appropriate for patients presenting in shock states. The hospital has successfully used this model of protocol-driven assessment and care with stroke, code blue, and rapid response teams.

Clinical Assessment

Initial rapid patient assessment includes signs of distress, level of consciousness, skin color, temperature, and moisture level. Heart rate, blood pressure, tissue oxygen saturation, and respiratory rate are the initial and most readily available methods of hemodynamic assessment and are considered non-invasive. This initial assessment allows the nurse to quickly determine the severity and urgency of the patient's needs. These may be altered in all forms of shock but do not specifically indicate the reason for the shock state. Thus, initial testing is necessary and determined by the patient's presentation to help differentiate the shock etiology and direct treatment (Jentzer et al., 2019; Nichol & Ahmed, 2014).

Clinical assessment and history-taking can be complex due to the unstable nature of CGS. The history given by the patient, including medications and past medical or surgical history, provides information to suggest a cardiac, septic, or hypovolemic cause for shock. Recent illness, fever, cough, or symptoms of infection could indicate an infectious etiology (Gyawali et al., 2019). Trauma, gastrointestinal bleeding, or gastroenteritis may indicate hypovolemic shock (Suresh, 2022). Cardiac disease history, chest pain, shortness of breath, diaphoresis, and peripheral edema can indicate cardiac reasons for shock. Relevant history is imperative to an appropriate diagnosis. Cardiac medications or immunosuppression therapy may alter symptoms and must be considered during this initial assessment (Henry et al., 2021; Kapur et al., 2022).

Hemodynamics

How the blood flows through the body or blood flow dynamics are called hemodynamics. These are influenced by the body's regulatory systems that constantly monitor and adjust to maintain adequate blood flow to the body's organs and tissues. There are options for hemodynamic assessment and monitoring. Invasive monitoring is performed by inserting an

arterial line, pulmonary artery catheter (PAC), or central venous catheter (Bertaina et al., 2022; Brener et al., 2020; Kashani et al., 2022). While invasive hemodynamics is beyond this project's scope, it is essential to note that the initial identification will assist in directing the need for further invasive testing and monitoring as part of the targeted treatment pathway. The initial nursing evaluation guided by the algorithm begins the path based on recognizing shock, acuity, and the urgency for differentiation and targeted treatment.

Non-invasive Hemodynamic Monitoring

Technological improvements have been made with this increasing interest in non-invasive monitoring methods. However, accuracy has been controversial and, in the setting of unstable CGS, has proven unreliable, likely due to vascular impedance, tachycardia, arrhythmias, or the interference of MCS (Bertaina et al., 2022). Non-invasive hemodynamic profiles and clinical assessment, including using the passive leg raise technique to assess fluid responsiveness, are comparable in approximately one-half of cases (Staudinger et al., 1998). Although, using bioimpedance has not been proven accurate in CGS (Piccirillo et al., 2022).

Invasive Hemodynamic Monitoring

Pulmonary artery catheters (PAC) have been used for over 50 years in the care of critically ill patients (Bertaina et al., 2022; Forrester, 2019; Headley & Ahrens, 2020). PACs were associated with increased mortality in the 1990s (Bertaina et al., 2022). This led to the routine use of PACs in ICU and surgery patients being discouraged (Allen et al., 2008; Bertaina et al., 2022; Marik, 2013). However, the need to assess and monitor these critical patients remained, causing an increased interest in non-invasive monitoring options as an alternative to invasive monitoring.

While past clinical trials have shown no benefit from the routine use of PAC in ICU and surgical patients, there have been mixed results in observational studies in CGS and advanced heart failure (van Diepen et al., 2017). PAC is recommended in undetermined shock etiology or when unresponsive to initial therapy attempts (van Diepen et al., 2017). The early use of invasive hemodynamics has been advocated in contemporary CGS management as the standard of care (Tehrani et al., 2020). CGS's complexity, instability, and life-threatening nature require quick diagnosis and targeted treatment. A PAC assists in the differentiation between CGS, hypovolemic, obstructive, and distributive shock.

Myocardial Point of Care Ultrasound/Echocardiography

Another non-invasive approach to myocardial assessment and differentiation of shock etiology is transthoracic echocardiography, which can reveal extensive and accurate information about myocardial function or strength of contraction, the major vessels in the chest, or the presence of pericardial effusion. A complete echocardiogram takes time and requires interpretation, most often provided by cardiologists (Ramadan et al., 2022). An alternative to the complete echocardiogram is the point of care ultrasound (POCUS), which can be performed quickly in the ED and provides timely information to help differentiate shock etiology. This abbreviated version of the complete echocardiogram can diagnose myocardium dysfunction, which is the hallmark of CGS. POCUS can assess the critical, time-sensitive condition of fluid volume status and ventricular dysfunction in hemodynamically unstable patients. The rapid bedside assessment can differentiate causes and evaluate the most immediate life-threatening conditions, allowing for optimized treatment (Geng et al., 2022). While POCUS and echocardiography are beyond the scope of a triage nurse, recognizing shock and the need for differentiation of shock phenotype falls upon the nurse performing the initial triage. The

standardization of the initial nurse triage process with the algorithm can facilitate rapid initiation of this diagnostic tool by the ED physician.

Shock Stage Classification

The symptoms at the initial patient presentation can be used to classify shock severity. The severity of the shock will assist in determining the urgency and necessity of initial treatment. The SCAI guidelines have been recognized and validated to assess and categorize shock into stages of severity. The stages progress from A, which represents a hemodynamically stable condition, and progress through E, indicating extremis or refractory shock. The risk of mortality increases as the severity of shock progresses (Jentzer et al., 2019; Jnetzer et al., 2022). The common language and classification by SCAI guidelines facilitate effective communication among care team members and have additionally been used for prognostic predictions. The Cardiogenic Shock Working Group Registry (Kapur et al., 2022) within the American College of Cardiology has adopted the SCAI guidelines (Appendix B).

Summary

While all shock can develop quickly and progress rapidly, the resulting tissue hypoperfusion leading to potential cell death is consistent. The overlapping clinical findings in the differing types of shock can cause uncertainty in diagnosis and selection of the definitive treatment path, making patient history and rapid assessment crucial to improved survival. Both septic and cardiogenic shock present similarly in the initial stages of shock. The specific treatment for each differs due to the underlying pathophysiology. While septic shock often requires aggressive fluid resuscitation, this treatment can worsen CGS. The severity of all types of shock and the duration of inadequate oxygenation to the organs and tissues determines the final mortality outcome (Rahulkumar et al., 2019). Utilizing the SCAI stages of shock facilitates

communication among caregivers and the urgency for treatment. As a patient advances to more severe shock states, the associated mortality increases (Jentzer et al., 2019). Prompt recognition of the symptoms of shock is essential to ensuring appropriate care. This begins with the initial nursing assessment and triage. Standardizing the triage assessment by nurses with an algorithm that guides the initial testing and classifies urgency is crucial to improving the survivability of all types of shock.

Methods

This DNP project included research and the development of an algorithm to guide early assessment, triage, and initial diagnostic testing to assist in the differentiation of CGS from other shock etiologies. Patient outcomes have improved in studies following the implementation of team-based protocols to direct treatment; thus, an algorithm to guide nurse initiate care for CGS may also show improved patient care (Basir et al., 2017; Hernandez et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2020; Osman et al., 2021; Tehrani et al., 2018; Tehrani et al., 2019). The project's objectives included the research and development of an algorithm to standardize the initial assessment, evaluation, differentiation, and staging of shock. Using nurse-initiated orders during triage provides additional information to facilitate the prompt differentiation of CGS and allow for targeted treatment initiation. In addition to the clinical criteria for shock, nurse-initiated orders are included.

After conducting the literature review, several components related to the treatment and identification of CGS, including clinical criteria, hemodynamic monitoring, diagnostic testing, and staging of shock based on acuity, stood out. Subject matter experts were consulted to determine if the components could be transferred to the hospital or ED triage setting to assist in developing an algorithm. Subject matter experts assisted in determining the type of algorithm and diagnostic testing that would be best suited for the ED triage nurse. Several protocols for the care and treatment of CGS were reviewed. The research indicated that the National Cardiogenic Shock Initiative (Basir et al., 2019) was the standard on which other CGS protocols were based. Components were taken from the National Cardiogenic Shock Initiative (Basir et al., 2019) to design the algorithm for this project.

The algorithm developed for the project was modeled after the facility's existing protocols for sepsis, STEMI, and stroke to provide continuity of the process used in the facility. This will assist staff in transitioning to a new protocol for CGS. The algorithm was developed as a flow chart, which includes clinical signs of shock, symptoms specific to CGS, nurse-initiated orders with diagnostic criteria, and stages of shock severity. These components were selected for the algorithm because they are noted to be the initial steps in identifying and differentiating shock etiology (Basir et al., 2019). Once drafted, subject matter experts reviewed the algorithm for accuracy and feasibility; they made suggestions for modifications, which were incorporated into the algorithm. Once the changes were made, the subject matter experts approved them. The algorithm was then sent to the ED educator and director to determine if it could be incorporated into the workflow. It was ultimately approved for pilot use, provided the staff received education regarding the algorithm. The education includes the use of the algorithm and the clinical criteria for the etiology and differentiation of CGS.

Based on the triage nurse's initial evaluation and guided by the algorithm, specific nurse-initiated orders for testing are used to evaluate severity and shock differentiation based on shock phenotype. Lactic acid is a marker of tissue hypoperfusion and shock independent of blood pressure (Galvagno et al., 2020). Rapid electrocardiogram (EKG) performance can reveal AMI/STEMI as a reason for the shock symptoms and is used to determine the need for an emergent cardiac angiogram with revascularization therapy (Alyahya et al., 2018; Coyne et al., 2015). A chest X-ray (CXR) can reveal signs of heart failure, such as an enlarged heart, pulmonary congestion due to fluid overload (Pan et al., 2021), or pneumonia caused by infection (Aggarwal & Srivastava, 2020), each requiring different treatments.

Additionally, a complete blood count (CBC) is used to evaluate potential infectious causes for septic shock as reflected in an elevation of white blood cells (WBC) and the differential cell types. It can also point to blood loss, indicated by low hemoglobin (HGB) or hematocrit (HCT) (Agnello et al., 2021; Lien et al., 2022). A comprehensive metabolic panel (CMP) can reveal electrolyte abnormalities and renal or hepatic dysfunction and indicate fluid volume status (Balci et al., 2013; Giordano et al., 2016; Shrimanker & Bhattarai, 2023). Cardiac-specific biomarkers can reveal possible cardiac factors contributing to shock. Brain natriuretic peptide (BNP) levels will be elevated when the heart muscle pumping is impaired due to heart failure (Khan & Rasool, 2021). Troponin levels can indicate acute myocardium injury or damage (Khan & Rasool, 2021).

The quality improvement (QI) project culminated in creating an algorithm to guide the initial assessment and care of patients presenting with symptoms of CGS. The project algorithm has been reviewed and approved for use by subject matter experts, staff, and management in the ED. Before triage nurses piloted the algorithm in the ED, nursing staff were educated on the assessment and identification of CGS and when to initiate orders.

Design

This QI project was designed to develop an algorithm for rapid, accurate identification of CGS. This algorithm consists of criteria for identifying shock, specific symptoms of CGS, nurse-initiated orders for suspected shock, and process steps to assist in differentiating CGS. After the algorithm was created, an accompanying training plan of evidence-based strategies will increase the knowledge, confidence, and comfort level of those nurses providing the initial evaluation and triage of patients presenting with CGS. The Iowa Model is used to guide the implementation of the QI project pilot.

Setting

The QI project was designed for a 222-bed nonprofit community hospital in Orange County, California, referred to as “the hospital” in this project. The target population of the algorithm was the nurses who assessed patients upon presentation and initial triage in the ED setting. The hospital is an acute care facility that provides a full range of services. The facility is designated as a cardiovascular receiving center, which ensures that patients experiencing STEMI are directed to this facility. The facility can provide emergency cardiac catheterization and cardiac surgery services 24 hours a day.

Participants

The algorithm targets nurses who have initial contact with adult patients presenting with symptoms of shock or a shock diagnosis (Appendix C). Adult patients will be defined as individuals 18 years or older.

Institutional Review Board Approval

The purpose of this DNP project was to research and develop an algorithm ready for implementation to guide the rapid identification and differentiation of CGS. No human subjects were involved; therefore, no confidentiality issues were present, and this project was determined not to require review from the Institutional Review Board at California State University, Los Angeles (Appendix D).

Measures

The algorithm was developed based on the evidence found during the literature review. It was modeled after other protocols currently in use at the hospital, including those for the care of patients presenting with STEMI, Stroke, and Code Crimson. The algorithm includes clinical findings of the shock, criteria specific to CGS, and a history of cardiac illness or conditions that

could put a patient at higher risk of CGS. Nurse-initiated orders and the SCAI stages of shock are detailed. Content experts reviewed the algorithm for accuracy and feasibility. Suggestions were incorporated into the algorithm. After the algorithm was complete, it was reviewed by the ED manager and director for ease of implementation.

Evaluation of the algorithm will occur after completion of the DNP program; however, it will consist of several components. The project will involve educating nurses on the signs and symptoms of CGS and implementing the algorithm. A pre and post-test (Appendix E & F) will be given to nurses immediately before the education and three weeks after implementing the algorithm. The pre-survey will assess baseline knowledge of CGS and nurse confidence in evaluating patients experiencing CGS. The post-survey will be administered after the nurses have had the opportunity to implement the algorithm. The post-survey will assess nurses' knowledge using questions taken from the pre-survey and assess nurses' confidence after using the algorithm. The post-survey will also include an assessment of the ease of use of the algorithm. Nurses will be able to identify facilitators and barriers to using the algorithm. Evaluation of the use of the algorithm will be conducted using a checklist that nurses must check off to show that they followed the seven steps of the algorithm (Appendix G).

Results

The initial phase of this project was completed in January 2024 and resulted in the development of an algorithm. This section will review the project results with a detailed explanation of the algorithm. The algorithm, which consists of seven components, was developed to standardize the initial triage nurse assessment, evaluation, differentiation, and staging of shock. The algorithm (Appendix C) begins with the clinical criteria for the initial identification shock. This includes the following criteria: systolic blood pressure (SBP) with evidence of tissue or end-organ hypoperfusion, as indicated by multiple physical symptoms that the nurse can visually assess. Following the initial recognition of shock, the nurse evaluates the patient for symptoms specific to CGS, such as chest pain and signs of fluid overload. Based on these presenting symptoms, the nurse-initiated orders for EKG, CXR, CBC, CMP, BMP, and troponin are placed. These nurse-initiated orders are placed immediately during the triage process as part of the intake. The nurse can order these tests before the doctor sees the patient, which expedites care and treatment for these critical patients. During triage, the nurse collects a cardiac history and medication list from the patient or caregiver, further identifying the patient at an increased risk of experiencing CGS.

The results of the nurse-initiated orders do not all come at once. Ideally, the EKG results take less than 10 minutes to obtain. These results can reveal if the patient is experiencing a STEMI, in which case the cardiologist must be notified immediately, and the patient must be prepared for emergent transfer to the cardiac catheterization lab for possible coronary revascularization to prevent further damage to the myocardium (Henry et al., 2021; Kapur et al., 2022). If the EKG does not indicate AMI/STEMI, the patient should be prepared for transfer to

the ICU for further testing and hemodynamic monitoring, including invasive monitoring and treatment.

Discussion

This QI project designed an algorithm to assist nurses in the early identification of CGS. The accompanying education will help triage nurses gain insight into their role in the early identification of shock, recognition of severity, and differentiation of CGS. The Iowa model was used as the guiding framework for this project as it provided the best means of the literature review reported improved patient outcomes when a protocol or algorithm was used to direct care (Basir et al., 2019; Tehrani et al., 2019; Truesdell et al., 2018). In the literature, an algorithm-based process used in STEMI/AMI and sepsis decreased patient mortality and morbidity (Evans, 2021; Henry et al., 2021). Upon completing the DNP program, the algorithm is ready to pilot in the present project.

Recommendations

Several recommendations were proposed for this DNP project. Triage nurses should be educated on the assessment and identification of CGS and when to initiate orders to ensure a timely diagnosis of CGS. The project will be implemented upon completion of the DNP program. Results will be collected and disseminated to key managers and other stakeholders interested in standardizing the process for identifying CGS in the ED. An additional recommendation is to expand the algorithm beyond the ED triage nurse to additional departments in the project hospital.

Staff Education

Pre-education surveys will be distributed among nursing staff who work in the ED, specifically the triage process. This survey will assess knowledge of CGS identification and confidence in recognizing CGS. The education plan will include clinical indications of shock in general and specific findings of CGS. Nurse-initiated orders available will be discussed, along

with indications for ordering specific tests. The algorithm steps and appropriate use will be clearly identified to enhance compliance with CGS's identification and classification process. After adopting the algorithm as a standard workflow, continued nursing education will occur as part of the nursing staff's annual competencies.

Plan for Evaluation

Following education and a three-week pilot period, a post-survey will be administered. The post-survey will include a comparison to a pre-education survey with open-ended feedback regarding the usability of the algorithm. A weekly checklist indicating the usage of the algorithm over the pilot period will be obtained from each nurse participating in the pilot. The data collected will be analyzed. If indicated, modifications to the algorithm and process will occur as indicated before adopting into practice. The expected result is that the algorithm will demonstrate improved patient outcomes and be adopted as a standard workflow. All staff will be educated on the clinical symptoms of shock, CGS, nurse-initiated orders, and the classification of shock before implementation. Data will continue to be collected and analyzed for periods of three months, six months, and one year and then according to hospital standards for long-term monitoring.

Implications

The use of algorithms to direct care has improved outcomes for patients in different populations, including those experiencing CGS (Basir et al., 2017; Basir et al., 2019; Brusca et al., 2022; Khariton et al., 2023). While many of the evaluated studies and guidelines included targeted treatment plans and advanced therapies, the essential first step is the recognition and early identification of shock. After the identification and differentiation of CGS, the targeted treatment follows. Shock identification and treatment in the initial stages of shock have shown

increased survivability compared to the advanced stages of shock (Jentzer et al., 2019). As shown in SSC, with each hour delay in treatment, mortality risk increased in patients with shock associated with sepsis (Evans et al., 2021). While the underlying pathology and treatment plans differ between CGS and septic shock, the underlying resultant hypoperfusion and high mortality.

Limitations

Several limitations have been noted in this QI pilot project. Time was a limitation. The project had a time constraint, which did not allow for the algorithm's implementation before the DNP program's completion. This resulted in a lack of data to support the adoption of the algorithm into standard practice in the ED. The pilot takes place in only one department, limiting the individuals being trained to use it. The nurse educator and manager evaluated the algorithm, which provided a narrow view of the algorithm; this limitation would have been mitigated by including emergency triage nurses in the evaluation process. There is potential for bias since the nurse educator and manager were the only two employees to determine the feasibility of implementation. Emergency triage nurses would have provided a working understanding of the feasibility of implementation since they work closely with patients.

Conclusion

CGS is a life-threatening condition that can progress rapidly and is associated with high mortality rates. The initial recognition of shock and steps to differentiate CGS from other shock phenotypes, as outlined in the algorithm, are essential to initiating appropriate therapy and improving survivability. While nurses do not make the diagnosis or order the treatments, they are at the frontline of determining the urgency of the patient's needs. Their prompt recognition and rapid actions are vital in determining the initial course of care the patient receives. The algorithm designed during this DNP project standardizes the process with easy-to-follow and replicable

steps that assist in the initial assessment and classification of the urgency of needs of the patient experiencing CGS. The algorithm included criteria for classifying the patient's shock stage, which dictated the urgency of the patient's treatment needs and helped provide early intervention and targeted treatment. The definitive diagnosis of CGS is crucial in delivering treatment directed at specific shock etiology, reducing mortality and morbidity, and decreasing hospital costs through improved patient outcomes.

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Appendix A

Iowa Model

Figure 2.2 Iowa Model of evidence-based practice to promote quality care. (Adapted with permission from Titler, M. G., Kleiber, C., Steelman, V., Rakel, B., Budreau, G., Everett, L. Q., . . . Goode, C. (2001). The Iowa model of evidence-based practice to promote quality care. *Critical Care Nursing Clinics of North America*, 13, 497–509.)

Appendix B

SCAI Shock Classification

Jentzer et al., 2022

Appendix C

Identification of Cardiogenic Shock Algorithm

Appendix D

IRB Exclusion

October 10, 2023

Hi Brenda,

Thank you for submitting the "Is My Project Human Subjects Research?" screening form. Based on the information submitted in this screening form, this project (*"Protocol Driven Team-Based Approach to Cardiogenic Shock Differentiation"*) does not seem to meet the definition of human subjects' research according to federal regulations (45 CFR 46), and therefore, does not require IRB review at this time.

Please reach out with any questions or concerns.

Best Regards,
Karina

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Appendix E

Pre-Education Survey

1. Name three clinical indicators for identification of shock.

2. Name three symptoms specific to CGS.

3. What patient history increases the risk of CGS? Name three

4. What is the expected first test for a patient presenting with chest pain?

5. How confident are you in recognizing CGS?

1	2	3	4	5
Very Unconfident	Unconfident	Neither Confident nor Unconfident	Confident	Very Confident

6. How confident are you in classifying shock according to SCAI shock criteria?

1	2	3	4	5
Very Unconfident	Unconfident	Neither Confident nor Unconfident	Confident	Very Confident

APPENDIX F

Post-Education Survey

1. Name three clinical indicators for identification of shock.

2. Name three symptoms specific to CGS.

3. What patient history increases the risk of CGS? Name three

4. What is the expected first test for a patient presenting with chest pain?

5. How confident are you in recognizing CGS?

1	2	3	4	5
Very Unconfident	Unconfident	Neither Confident nor Unconfident	Confident	Very Confident

6. How confident are you in classifying shock according to SCAI shock criteria?

1	2	3	4	5
Very Unconfident	Unconfident	Neither Confident nor Unconfident	Confident	Very Confident

7. How easy is the algorithm to follow?

1	2	3	4	5
Very Difficult	Difficult	Neither Difficulty nor Easy	Easy	Very Easy

8. What are the barriers you encountered when using the algorithm?

9. Please provide feedback on how to improve the CGS identification process.

APPENDIX G**Post-Implementation Checklist**

Date: _____ Week of pilot: _____ Week of your use: _____

1. How many patients presented with clinical shock indicators for the week?

2. How many of the patients had symptoms specific to CGS?

3. How many of the patients received the nurse-initiated orders from you?